

RISK MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY IN THE SYSTEM OF ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE COMPANIES

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Abstract: The paper considers the content and approaches to the definition of the concepts of "investment", "investment activity". The importance and methods of risk management of the company's investment activity as a tool to ensure its economic security are disclosed.

Keywords: economic security, investment, risks, management, investors.

There are various approaches to defining the concept of investment. It is customary to divide investments by the term and purpose of the investment:

- for real or capital-forming - intended for the acquisition of assets and investments in advertising, new developments, training, research;
- portfolio – implies the purchase of securities;
- gross – total investments for reimbursement and increase of fixed capital;
- net – represents gross investment minus depreciation.

According to the form, the following types of investments are allocated:

cash or cash equivalents;

land; equipment, property, buildings, buildings;

patents, trademarks, licenses and other proprietary rights.

Investments play an important role in the process of forming and building productive capacity and, consequently, contribute to economic growth and financial recovery. These are the financial means by which the real capital of society increases, they are directed to the expansion or modernization of the production apparatus. In the definition under consideration, investment activity is demonstrated from the beginning of its implementation — investment of funds as an investment up to the receipt of income (other useful effect) as the final result of the investor's activity.

The investment activity of the enterprise is aimed at the search and implementation of optimal and effective management methods, as well as the search for objects whose financing will make it possible to obtain a significant financial return (additional profit). A distinctive feature of investment activity is that it is costly and risky.

The first is that there is no investment without costs. To begin with, you should invest, and only after (if the calculations were correct) the costs incurred will pay off.

Secondly, it is impossible to foresee all the circumstances that an investor will expect in the future, there is a possibility that the investments made will be partially or completely lost (that is, there are investment risks).

The term "investment activity" is associated with such concepts as the subject and the object of investment, which in market conditions determine the specifics and distinctive features of investment activity. The subject of investment activity is an individual or a legal entity involved in investment relations. The subject is a direct participant in the process and one of the parties to the investment transaction. The objects of the company's investment activity include newly developed and modernized fixed assets, and working capital, targeted cash deposits, scientific and technical products, securities and other property objects, as well as property rights and intellectual property rights. The choice of investment objects for today is huge, but the resources of any organization are limited. In this regard, much attention is paid to the formation and optimization of the investment portfolio. The effectiveness and quick return on investment, first of all, is influenced by the correct assessment of the prospects of the investment project. The essence of investment activity consists in attracting, competent distribution, optimal application and objective analysis of investment risks. Risk management is part of the overall management decision-making process and is associated with unforeseen events, the occurrence of which it is impossible to know in advance with absolute accuracy.

Risk management is considered as a system for assessing adverse impacts and making management decisions on this basis that contribute to reducing the probability of losses to a minimum level. If the occurrence of losses cannot be avoided completely, the task of risk management becomes their maximum reduction. Risk management is more about predicting what to expect and at the same time preparing for it accordingly, and not just reactionary reaction at all. An optimal risk management system implies building a company management scheme in which the main task is to prevent all kinds of problems.

The method of investment risk management at the enterprise directly determines the business entity, taking into account such factors as the discount rate, the availability of investment resources in sufficient quantity and appropriate quality, the payback period of investments and others. When developing a company's development strategy and risk management methods, managers, as a rule, take as a basis a certain standard formed on the basis of their knowledge and experience.

Using a ready-made template, the manager will quickly resolve all the issues that have arisen.

Non-standard situations require the adoption of more extraordinary decisions that are most suitable for the circumstances. The economic security of an enterprise depends on effective and safe investment activity in general, its ability to prevent threats, avoid risks and the ability to achieve its goals in a competitive and risky environment. One of the ways that helps the company to localize and prevent various threats to the economic security of enterprises is the method of strategic organizational changes, which involves structural modifications in the organization.

With this method, there will be a kind of distribution of risks and threats to ensure the economic security of enterprises in order to minimize the scale of their concentration. It is also possible to single out the insurance method as a way to ensure economic security. It combines insurance and non-insurance risks of the enterprise, thus, it is a combination of insurance and financial protection.

As a result of using this method, the company insures not only traditional risks, for example, accident risks, but also speculative ones, because the foreign exchange market provides for both partial losses and winnings, which provides a kind of compensation for losses. In order to reduce the amount of possible losses, project managers and investors evaluate the idea in terms of possible risks and associated damages.

From all of the above, we can conclude that for the economic security of investment activities, the company is obliged to form investment risk management at a high level. It is necessary to be able to choose a more acceptable method of managing investment risks, taking into account absolutely all conditions affecting investment activity.

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